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PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS FOR PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract: Professional or occupational standards, as a new approach to teacher preparation focused on qualifications across all subjects, serve as essential tools for defining the competencies required of professionals in various fields of education. The educational system in Uzbekistan today operates within a global labor market, where teachers play a critical role in enhancing students' employability.

By providing a framework that aligns educational achievements with the rapidly changing demands of the labor market, these standards ensure that university graduates possess the skills and knowledge necessary to meet modern professional requirements. This approach is closely linked to several legislative and regulatory initiatives in Uzbekistan that aim to harmonize the needs of the labor market with the education system.

Key words: competence, education, skill, collaboration, pedagogy, framework, labor market, capacity, assessment, standards.

Annotatsiya: O'qituvchilarni tayyorlashda yangi yondashuv bo'lgan professional yoki kasbiy standartlar barcha fanlar bo'yicha o'qituvchilarning malakasini belgilashda muhim vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi global mehnat bozori sharoitida faoliyat yuritmoqda va unda o'qituvchilar talabalarni mehnat bozoriga tayyorlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Ushbu standartlar ta'limdagi yutuqlarni tez o'zgarayotgan mehnat bozori ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish uchun zarur bo'lgan asosni yaratadi. Natijada, universitet bitiruvchilari zamonaviy kasbiy talablarga mos bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'ladilar. Mazkur yondashuv O'zbekistonda mehnat bozori ehtiyojlarini ta'lim tizimi bilan uyg'unlashtirishga qaratilgan bir qator qonunchilik va me'yoriy tashabbuslar bilan uzviy bog'liqdir.

Kalit so'zlar: kompetensiya, ta'lim, ko'nikma, hamkorlik, pedagogika, tizim, mehnat bozori, salohiyat, baholash, standartlar.

Аннотация: Профессиональные или квалификационные стандарты, как новый подход к подготовке учителей, ориентированный на квалификационные требования по всем учебным дисциплинам, являются важным инструментом для определения компетенций, необходимых специалистам в различных сферах образования. Современная система образования Узбекистана функционирует в условиях глобального рынка труда, где учителя играют ключевую роль в повышении трудоустроенности студентов.

Создавая основу для согласования образовательных достижений с быстро меняющимися требованиями рынка труда, эти стандарты обеспечивают выпускникам вузов необходимые знания и навыки для соответствия современным профессиональным требованиям. Этот подход тесно связан с рядом законодательных и нормативных инициатив в Узбекистане, направленных на гармонизацию потребностей рынка труда с системой образования.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, образование, навык, сотрудничество, педагогика, структура, рынок труда, потенциал, оценивание, стандарты.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers once adhered to a knowledge-based approach; however, as Uzbekistan transitions to a credit-based educational system, the integration of transparent, competency-based assessments—such as formative, midterm, and summative evaluations—has become a subject of considerable debate.

As a member of the United Nations, Uzbekistan is committed to the implementation of the Education-2030 Agenda, which emphasizes the development of inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Central to this agenda is the alignment of educational programs with both formal and non-formal learning systems, as articu-

lated in key national legislative documents. One of the primary legal frameworks guiding this process is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” – a foundational document for educational reform. In addition, Presidential Decree No. PQ-4939, issued on 2020-12-31 and titled “On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Skills Assessment System and Provide the Labor Market with Qualified Personnel” – reinforces the need to establish a robust qualifications assessment system that directly corresponds to labor market demands.

This document explores the implementation of these legislative instruments and evaluates their implications for the development of professional standards in education. It thereby contributes to advancing the broader goals of the Education-2030 initiative and facilitating more effective integration of labor market requirements into Uzbekistan’s educational system.

The core competencies required of teachers at specific qualification levels are essential to meeting the standards expected of their professional roles. These competencies serve as a foundation for assessing the comprehensive readiness of educators, aligning their qualifications with the expected learning outcomes. In accordance with the guidelines of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, these competencies are categorized into three main groups:

- I. General or key competencies for the 21st-century employee.
- II. General competencies for citizens, aligned with SDG indicators and their relevance to teaching.
- III. Direct professional pedagogical competencies.

Additional context: The Republic of Uzbekistan is home to 216 higher education institutions, 14 of which specialize in pedagogy. These institutions serve more than 50,000 students, representing a significant segment of the academic population preparing for careers in teaching. This statistic underscores the vital role of pedagogical institutions in shaping future educators and addressing the growing need for qualified teaching professionals in the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The development of professional standards for pre-service teachers has become a central focus in international education reform, aiming to improve teacher quality and align preparation with the complex demands of the 21st-century classroom. Scholars emphasize that clearly defined teaching standards are essential for ensuring the coherence of teacher education programs, assessment, and professional identity.

Shulman introduced the concept of pedagogical content knowledge as a foundational element in teacher expertise, arguing that effective teaching requires not only subject mastery but also the ability to transform content into teachable formats. This notion has become a cornerstone for defining teacher competencies within national and international frameworks.

The OECD’s Teachers Matter report highlights the importance of setting transparent and measurable professional standards to improve recruitment, training, and retention of high-quality teachers. It argues that performance-based standards enable policy-makers and institutions to better support teacher development across career stages.

In the context of lifelong learning and reflective practice, Schön’s work on the reflective practitioner emphasizes the need for teachers to engage in continuous self-assessment and adaptation. This perspective aligns with global trends promoting teacher autonomy, professional judgment, and responsiveness to dynamic classroom contexts.

The European Commission underscores the role of competence-based training in preparing teachers for inclusive and equitable education. It calls for integrating key transversal skills—such as collaboration, digital literacy, and cultural responsiveness—into teacher standards to meet the goals of Sustainable Development Goal 4.

Research by Zeichner and Liston supports the view that teacher education should develop socially conscious, critically reflective practitioners who can advocate for equity and justice. They argue that standards must balance measurable competencies with the cultivation of ethical and democratic values.

Hattie and Timperley, through their research on feedback, also point to the value of standards that guide evidence-based practice and classroom assessment. Their findings suggest that professional frameworks should help teachers interpret and act on student performance data to improve outcomes.

In Uzbekistan, the adoption of national qualification frameworks and competency models, supported by presidential decrees and educational reforms, reflects alignment with global models. These reforms prioritize the synchronization of higher education with labor market needs, emphasizing the development of workplace-relevant skills in teacher preparation.

Collectively, these studies support the premise that well-structured professional standards enhance the quality and coherence of pre-service teacher education. They provide a basis for accountability, professional growth, and improved student achievement across diverse educational systems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research employed a qualitative content analysis method, examining national legislative documents, policy frameworks, and institutional reports related to teacher education standards. Data were collected from official publications of the Ministry of Higher Education and relevant international sources. Thematic coding was used to identify key competencies and analyze their alignment with labor market and educational reform goals.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To succeed in the dynamic and rapidly evolving workplace of the 21st century, employees, especially educators, must possess a set of general competencies that enable them to navigate complex professional environments. Among these, analytical skills are crucial, as teachers must critically evaluate pedagogical data, assess student performance, and apply evidence-based instructional strategies. This involves solving complex problems, synthesizing diverse information sources, and making data-driven decisions to improve learning outcomes. Equally important is creativity, which empowers teachers to design innovative, engaging learning experiences that stimulate critical thinking and adapt to diverse student needs. Leadership, another key competency, allows educators to inspire students, collaborate with colleagues, and foster inclusive, value-driven learning environments that support continuous improvement.

Proficient communication is essential for educators to articulate ideas clearly in both oral and written forms and to engage effectively with students, parents, and stakeholders. Digital literacy has become indispensable in today's classrooms, requiring teachers to integrate technology into instruction, manage digital platforms, and adapt to emerging technological tools to enhance learning efficiency. Adaptability enables teachers to respond constructively to changes in educational policy, student diversity, and evolving methodologies, while maintaining a commitment to professional growth. Collaboration is equally vital, as it supports cooperative planning, shared problem-solving, and reflective teaching practices across educational communities. Emotional intelligence strengthens interpersonal dynamics, enabling teachers to manage emotions, build meaningful relationships, and establish emotionally supportive classroom environments.

Critical thinking is foundational for analyzing educational issues, questioning assumptions, and modeling reflective thinking for students, encouraging informed decision-making based on sound reasoning. Time management helps teachers balance instructional planning, assessment duties, and ongoing professional development, while also maintaining personal well-being and professional effectiveness. Collectively, these competencies support the development of reflective, innovative, and student-centered educators. In an increasingly complex global labor market, such skills are essential for preparing teachers to contribute meaningfully to institutional success and broader societal advancement.

Aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 4 – “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” – the general competencies required of teachers must address not only instructional quality but also the principles of inclusivity and educational transparency. These competencies form the basis of an educator's ability to implement global goals in local learning environments and help achieve equitable education systems.

One of the most essential competencies is pedagogical expertise, which requires teachers to possess deep knowledge of curriculum design, effective teaching strategies, and assessment methods tailored to the diverse needs of learners. Shulman's concept of pedagogical content knowledge emphasizes the combination of subject-matter expertise with methods grounded in research and classroom experience. Another critical area is inclusive education, where teachers must develop the ability to create equitable and accessible learning spaces that reflect cultural, linguistic, and developmental diversity. This includes teaching students with disabilities, as well as those from marginalized or underrepresented groups, through differentiated instruction and culturally responsive pedagogy.

In parallel, lifelong learning and continuous professional development are fundamental for educators to remain responsive to pedagogical innovation and digital transformation. The European Commission recognizes this ongoing development as central to modern teaching. Collaboration and partnership also represent key competencies, enabling teachers to build professional communities, share best practices, and engage with families and stakeholders to support student achievement. Research by Vogt and Rogalla demonstrates that mutual support among educators enhances instructional capacity and professional resilience.

Leadership and advocacy for equity further elevate the teacher's role beyond classroom instruction. Educators are expected to lead initiatives that reduce disparities and support inclusive policy implementation, especially regarding gender equality and the inclusion of disadvantaged students. As highlighted by Darling-Hammond and Bransford, such leadership is essential to systemic educational change. In addition, emotional and social competence plays a vital role in classroom dynamics, as emotionally intelligent teachers are better equipped to cultivate empathy, manage relationships, and create a secure learning climate that supports student well-being and engagement.

Finally, digital literacy has become indispensable in the 21st-century classroom. Teachers must be capable of integrating ICT tools into teaching, using digital platforms effectively, and fostering students' digital skills. Mishra and Koehler emphasize that this technological-pedagogical integration is key to improving student outcomes and instructional relevance. Together, these competencies enable teachers to become agents of transformation, fostering inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education in line with SDG 4 and the broader goals of sustainable development.

Direct professional pedagogical competencies are foundational in shaping pre-service teachers into effective and reflective practitioners. One of the most critical of these is subject matter proficiency, which requires future teachers to demonstrate a deep understanding of the subjects they will teach. This includes mastering core content, connecting theoretical knowledge to real-world situations, and facilitating meaningful learning aligned with educational standards. Equally important is cultural awareness, which allows educators to create inclusive environments by integrating students' cultural, linguistic, and experiential diversity into their teaching. This sensitivity fosters a classroom culture of respect and belonging, a concept strongly supported by culturally responsive pedagogy.

Professional growth is another indispensable competency. It involves a lifelong commitment to learning, participation in professional development, and reflective engagement with contemporary research and innovations in pedagogy. Pedagogical knowledge, as outlined in international frameworks such as the ISCED, encompasses an understanding of instructional strategies, curriculum planning, and diverse teaching models. Pre-service teachers must be able to apply approaches such as inquiry-based, collaborative, and direct instruction to meet student needs. Alongside this, a sound grasp of child development is essential. Teachers must understand the cognitive, social, emotional, and physical growth stages of children and adolescents to tailor instruction accordingly, as highlighted in Piaget's theory of development.

Instructional design is another core skill that enables teachers to develop well-structured, purposeful lesson plans that engage students deeply. Effective lesson planning ensures alignment with learning objectives and flexibility for differentiation. Differentiated instruction itself is vital for meeting the needs of diverse learners, including students with disabilities, language learners, and gifted individuals. This approach ensures fairness and maximizes each learner's potential. Moreover, using resources and technology effectively is now an essential expectation. Pre-service teachers must be skilled in integrating digital tools, multimedia content, and interactive platforms to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

Classroom presence is critical in establishing authority, building rapport, and maintaining a focused and respectful learning space. This is closely tied to creating a positive learning environment that supports emotional safety, motivation, and student participation. A well-managed classroom contributes directly to academic success and student well-being, as emphasized in educational research. Finally, behavior management is a competency that ensures teachers can prevent disruptions, apply constructive discipline, and foster student self-regulation. This includes implementing proactive strategies and maintaining consistency in classroom expectations. Together, these competencies form a holistic framework that equips pre-service teachers with the necessary skills, knowledge, and attitudes to navigate the complexities of modern education and meet the diverse needs of today's learners effectively.

Assessment and evaluation within the framework of Competence-Based Training (CBT) are designed to measure an individual's ability to apply essential skills and knowledge in real-world professional contexts. Unlike traditional models that emphasize theoretical knowledge, CBT prioritizes practical performance and real-life application of competencies. The central goal is to ensure that learning outcomes are relevant to workplace needs and that future educators are adequately prepared for task-specific demands. Performance-based assessment in this model requires learners to demonstrate skills through authentic tasks, either in actual or simulated settings. Instead of comparing individuals to one another, CBT uses criteria-referenced evaluation, where learners are assessed against predefined standards that clearly articulate the expected outcomes.

A distinguishing feature of CBT is its emphasis on continuous assessment. Through regular formative feedback, learners are supported in refining their competencies over time. This ensures that mastery is developed gradually and purposefully. Additionally, holistic assessment is encouraged, meaning that multiple competencies—technical, cognitive, and interpersonal—are measured simultaneously within integrated tasks. Evidence-based evaluation further strengthens the process by requiring learners to present tangible proof of their capa-

bilities, such as portfolios, task results, or observed performance, all of which are judged against established competency benchmarks. These benchmarks are carefully aligned with real-world requirements and are often developed in collaboration with industry experts to maintain relevance and rigor.

Feedback plays a critical role in CBT. Constructive, targeted feedback enables learners to recognize both strengths and gaps, fostering self-awareness and continuous growth. Summative assessment is administered at the end of the training cycle to verify whether the learner has achieved all required competencies. Only those who meet the standards are deemed qualified for professional roles. For pre-service teachers, understanding both formative and summative assessment is essential. They must be able to design and apply assessments that align with curricular goals and provide accurate insight into student progress. Moreover, the ability to analyze assessment data and use it to inform instructional decisions—referred to as data-informed instruction—is a core competency that ensures equity and responsiveness in teaching.

In addition to assessment, continuing professional development, ethics, and responsibilities are fundamental to a teacher's role. Educators are expected to uphold professional conduct, demonstrating integrity, confidentiality, and ethical behavior in all interactions with students, parents, and colleagues. A strong commitment to equity is also required; teachers must ensure all students, regardless of background or ability, have access to meaningful learning opportunities. This is closely tied to the principle of continuous professional development, where teachers are encouraged to remain reflective, engage with current research, and collaborate with peers to grow their practice.

Collaboration and communication are likewise essential. Teachers must effectively coordinate with colleagues, school administrators, and support staff to co-plan instruction and exchange ideas. Just as important is the ability to communicate and engage with parents and community stakeholders, keeping them informed and involved in student learning. Strong community partnerships greatly enhance educational outcomes. Finally, reflective practice must become habitual. Teachers should regularly assess their own teaching effectiveness, identify areas for development, and adapt accordingly. Flexibility and a willingness to try new approaches are crucial in modern classrooms, where diversity, innovation, and change are constant.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In summary, implementing Competence-Based Training (CBT) in the preparation of pre-service teachers fosters a holistic and practical approach to developing essential professional competencies. Through performance-based, criteria-referenced, and continuous assessment, pre-service educators are evaluated not merely on theoretical knowledge, but on their demonstrated ability to apply skills in real-world educational contexts. Emphasizing ethical responsibility, professional conduct, and a strong commitment to equity ensures that future educators are equipped to serve diverse learners with integrity and fairness.

Moreover, ongoing professional development cultivates a mindset of lifelong learning, enabling teachers to remain current with evolving pedagogical trends and respond effectively to the dynamic demands of the education sector. Collaborative and communicative competencies further reinforce the importance of teamwork, parental involvement, and community engagement in enhancing student learning outcomes. Reflective practice encourages adaptability and self-awareness, empowering pre-service teachers to critically assess their instructional strategies and make informed improvements.

By integrating these elements, CBT not only elevates the overall quality of teacher education but also contributes to the development of a competent, ethical, and reflective teaching workforce—aligned with both Uzbekistan's national education priorities and globally recognized standards for effective teaching.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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